

Principals' Perception of School Plant Management Practices in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

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Abstract

This study examined Principals' Perception of School Plant Management Practices in Public Senior Secondary School in Rivers State. The population comprised of 321 male principals and 420 female principals making total of 741 in the 23 education zones in Rivers State. The sample comprises 270 male principals and 354 female principals making total of 624 in 15 education zones in Rivers State using random sampling technique. Data were collected using the researcher's self-constructed questionnaire titled. "The Principal's Perception of School Plant Management Practices Questionnaire (PPSPMPQ)" from the respondents. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Two research questions were structured to guide the study and consequently two null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance. Data were analyzed using the mean and standard deviation to answer the two research questions posed while t-test statistics was used to test the two null hypothesis formulated at 0.05 level of significance level. The analysis of data revealed the acceptance of all the null hypothesis, thereby showing that there were no significant difference found in the mean perception of male and female principals on the adequacy of school plants, utilization of school plants and availability of school plants in the management practices in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Findings were that principals perceive the adequacy of school plants on its management practices. Also that male and female principals perceive the availability of school plants and they discovered that adequate utilization of school plants has broaden their scope of learning performance in academic work. Therefore, the researchers recommend that the construction of more administrative blocks to accommodate the different staff offices should be built by the state government. Also, provision of school plants that would enhance teaching and learning process should be encouraged by the state government through the Ministry of Education and Rivers State Senior Secondary School board.

Keyword: Principals, School plant, Management practices, Secondary School.

Introduction

School plant is liken to the school site, building, playground, equipment and other school needs provided for effective and efficient teaching and learning as described by (Onwurah, 2004).

Onwurah (2004) further explained that school plant is the space interpretation of the curriculum, observing that the programs of the school are expressed through the school plant. According to Ajayi (2007) who stressed that school plant comprises of machinery which includes machines and tools used in the workshop, in addition to duplicating machines. It is maintained that school site, which is the landscape on which the school structure are buildings, equipment, furniture, vehicles of various type, electrical fittings, books, water supply, infrastructure, and accessories like the playgrounds, farms, parks are parts of the school plant (Yusuf, 2008). Unfortunately, there are inadequate provision of classrooms and school buildings for teaching and learning to take place effectively in the state. The state government could not provide enough buildings to accommodate their growing population of students and teachers rather; most of the secondary schools are experiencing dilapidated buildings, very poor facilities for teaching and learning purposes and there was no meaningful policy on school plant management by the school principals' (Nwagwu, 2018).

Idoko (2005) posited that one of the primary functions of the principals is the management and maintenance of school plant because the success or failure of the education system depends on the proper management of the schools by the principals. The school plant in this study are the buildings, compound, staff offices, laboratories, libraries, and classrooms which is the school facilities that brings about effective teaching and learning in the secondary schools. Dilapidated school buildings have to be removed and expanded while new ones have to be sited and established to accommodate the over-populated students. In the words of Olatunji (2017) school plant management practices involves the number of on-going and related activities determining the need for school plant educational program.

The responsibility of managing the school plant rests with the principals. The principal may not be knowledgeable in some aspects of school plant management practices such as school facilities design and building construction but his/her input and in some cases the inputs of other school staff during decision making in these area may be necessary as it is the principal and the school staff that will make use of the buildings after their completion (Ani, 2018). The school plant must also be open for use effectively and efficiently on daily basis and that it is kept neat and tidy always. Effective school plant management practices ensures that school facilities are effectively used for teaching and learning with little or no interruption. These implies that efficient management practices of school plant is mandatory in order to make the school pleasant, safe and a comfortable center for community's activities (Ijekpa & Mkpa, 2020).

Education industry as stated by Fafunwa (2018) is like the industrial sector that requires the use of human, material and financial resources for production to take place. The school plant which refers to the physical facilities available in the school such as school buildings, equipment, school site, laboratories, libraries etc., can be likened to the capital in an industrial sector. Adequate and appropriate school plants are indispensable in the educational process. Indeed, proper management of school plant in the secondary schools will not only boost the morale of teachers and students but will also ensure that objectives of the school system are been achieved (Allagoa, 2017).

The federal government in its second and third National Development plans noted the inadequacy of school plant and its impact on educational quality in the country. Consequently, it made provision for expanding and improving the existing school plant in its third National plan (Fafunwa, 2018). Efforts of the Federal and State Government in the country seem not to have done enough towards providing adequate school plant in the country as a recent observation of the Education Sector Support program in Nigeria (ESSPIN) which shows in respect of some states that were studied by members of the groups. According to ESSPIN (2009) report shows that most school buildings are in poor condition. One of the main reasons for the current chronic situation is that the education sector, particularly infrastructure suffered from an approximately 20 years period of neglect during the military regime especially in Rivers State. The buildings that have been constructed in recent years are also in very poor quality. They have been badly built because of poor procurement practices, poor management of construction, poor workmanship, the use of low quality materials, lack of supervision during construction even where buildings have been constructed to an acceptable standard (generally those more than 20 years old) there has been a severe lack of maintenance which has resulted in many buildings being in a state of disrepair and thus having a reduced life span (Enaohwo & Eferokaya, 2014). The unattractive and outmoded school plants devoid of necessary facilities, poor landscaping, dilapidated walls and roofs blown off by storm use to be a common sight in our public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

According to Fafunwa, (2018), education is the greatest investment that any nation can make for the rapid development of its economic, political, sociological and human resources. It follows therefore that even from the global point of view, education is very much of vital importance in the sense that one of the factors to consider a country as being developed or advanced is its rate of literacy. The National Policy on Education (2013) states that the Federal Government of Nigeria has adopted education as an instrument of excellence. The state government is committed to its pledge in creating an education system that will guarantee equal educational development. The special attention given to education demonstrates the government's active involvement in the sector. There was also the pledge of expanded facilities for education aimed principally at equalizing individual access to education throughout Rivers State, in the same vein, government advocated the reform of the general education in the bid to make it more responsible and responsive to the socioeconomic needs of the both indigenes and non-indigenes (Allagoa, 2017). They also advocated the need for strengthening the machinery for educational development in the state.

Over the years, Rivers State has witnessed the proliferation of secondary schools caused by political pressure. A by-product of these proliferations is the fact that secondary education in the state considerably underwent in unprecedented growth rate. Ani, (2018) explained that enrolment became more than double, when this happens the attendance danger is that quality is likely sacrificed for mediocrity and mass production and over-stretched the issue of the plant available. Today, a visit to any of the secondary schools within the state reveals that most of the school plants are not well kept and maintained. Ozigi (2011) explained that at a common sight of school plant is a picture of broken down windows, vandalized doors, broken lockers, un-kept premises, flooded

school compound being submerged in mud, dilapidated building etc., all these are induced by improper planning and management practices of school plant by the school administrators (principals).

According to Corbally (2010) the concept of school plant is described as the site, buildings, the equipment and all the essential structures, permanent and semi-permanent as well as such machines and laboratory equipment, the blackboard/chalkboard needed for effective teaching and learning. In the words of Amanchukwu and Ololube (2015) they stated that one of the strongest problems with the educational system is the inappropriate school plant planning. They explained that school plant management requires good leadership, effective monitoring culture, preventive and predictive maintenance. They viewed the problem of school plant management practice to be over crowded, non-delegation of tasks by the principal to staff, vandalism property by students and community youths

Yusuf (2008) defined school plant as space interpretation of the school curriculum. It will be impossible for the curriculum to be implemented if the physical facilities required for teaching and learning are not available. Absence of school plant makes teaching ineffective and desired learning will not take place (Oddie, 2014). In Rivers State secondary school, we experienced over population of students and of course, poor teaching and learning manifested itself. Teachers could not move around to give the learners individual help where needed because there is no space in between the desk in the classroom. School plant is all embracing in the fact that it comprises every single item starting from the gate of the school to the walls covering the school compound.

NOUN Module (2011) stated that for effective teaching and learning in the educational system, the functions of the school plant is very important, since it takes care of the intellectual development of the child while others takes care of all the social, emotional, physical and sometimes spiritual well-being of the students. It therefore allowed that every school plant has a unique function to perform. Ogie (2015) explained that the uniqueness and relevance of each school plant is embedded in the functions. For instance, the classroom houses the students, thereby protecting them from environmental hazards. It gives comfort and holds all teaching equipment that aids the students in their learning.

Statement of the Problem

There has been a drastic decline in some of the essential services required in Rivers State educational system. These have affected students' performance in the three public examinations in the sense that, the classroom is overcrowded, distractions experienced by students and teachers due to inconveniences in the classroom, inadequate facilities, and the achievement of pre-specified curriculum objectives becomes unattainable, inevitably leading to students failure (Yusuf, 2008). However, students' performance in these three public examinations Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board (JAMB), National Examination Council (NECO) and West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) is not encouraging in the past years which has posed serious challenge in the state. Public secondary schools in Rivers State are funded by the state government. They also select their own teachers who take care of the students and the facilities in the school

compound. The state government is expected to take full control of those secondary schools by providing all the necessary infrastructures for effective teaching and learning, some of these infrastructures are non-existent in some schools and at times the existing ones are in a very bad state. For the past few years the results of these three examinations Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board (JAMB), National Examination Council (NECO) and West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) were nothing to write home about. Other factors that have affected the students' performance such as indiscipline which Amanchukwu and Ololube (2015) revealed that led to the declining standard of education. There is actual lack of school plant management practices and the few available ones are in terrible state.

The management of school plant by principals' is an essential aspect of schools and if poorly done due to non-existence of school plant or lack of maintenance the situation will be chaotic. Hence, schools plants within the state are deteriorated, inadequate buildings and equipment, bad maintenance culture etc. It becomes very clear that provision of quality educational system and their usage should be taken seriously within the state for students to measure up creditably in the comity of nations. The problem of inadequate school plant is exacerbated by the fact that some principals', teachers, and students appear to take upkeep lightly. Efforts have been made to improve the school plant to influence students' performance, but most of these efforts appear ineffective. It is therefore against this backdrop that the researchers examine principal's perception of school plant management practices in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The aim of this study was to assess principals' perception of school plant management practices in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of the study was to;

1. Determine the extent of principals' perception on the adequacy of school plant management practices in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. Examine the level of principals' perception on the availability of school plant management practices in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study;

1. To what extent do principals perceive the adequacy of school plant management practices in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. To what extent do principals perceive the availability of school plants management practices in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

- H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the perception of male and female principals on the adequacy of school plant management practices of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the perception of male and female principals on the availability of school plant management practices of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Methodology

The research design used for this study was the descriptive survey design. The total population of the study consisted of 321 male principals and 420 female principals' was achieved through the use of stratified random sampling technique. The sample size of 624 principals' were selected from 15 education zones. Population of the study consisted of 741 of the 23 education zones in Rivers State. A self-developed questionnaire titled "Principals' Perception of School Plant Management Practice questionnaire (PPSPMPQ)" was used to elicit data from the respondents. The instrument was validated by two experts in the department of educational management and measurement and evaluation. The instrument had two sections: section A and B. Section A consisted of demographic information of the respondents while section B contained questionnaire items based on the research questions. The response scale was structured on a 4- point likert rating scale of strongly Agree [SA], Agree [A], Disagree [D] and Strongly Disagree [SD] with values of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. Cronbach Alpha was used to test the reliability of the instrument which gave reliability indexes of 0.99 and 0.91 mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions with a criterion mean of 2.50. Questionnaire items with mean scores below 2.50 denoted Disagreed while 2.50 and above signified Agreed, the hypotheses were tested using z test statistic at 0.005 level of significance. Analyzed data with calculated z value above the z critical value of 1.96 were rejected and below 1.96 were accepted.

Research Question 1

To what extent do principals' perceive the adequacy of school plant management practices in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 1: shows the responses of the respondents to research questionnaire item 1-5 Summary of descriptive statistics for principals’ perception on the adequacy of school plant management practices

	STATEMENTS	MALE PRINCIPALS		FEMALE PRINCIPALS		TOTAL/MEAN		
		M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	RMK
1	Administrative blocks are adequate for different department.	3.35	0.84	3.03	0.76	3.19	0.80	A
2	The school possess all the requisite gadgets needed to make learning enjoyable.	3.22	0.81	3.03	0.76	3.13	0.78	A
	Recreational facilities of the School affords students opportunity to be vast in sports.						0.80	A
4	Office equipment for administrative functions are adequate.	3.31	0.83	3.06	0.77	3.19		
		3.40	0.85	3.28	0.82	3.34	0.81	A
5	Classrooms are sufficient for students to be split into smaller units for effective teaching and learning.	3.10	0.73	3.13	0.78	3.02	0.76	A
	Grand Mean/SD	16.38	4.06	15.53	3.89	15.87	4.76	

Mean 3.35 and 3.03 shows that the respondents agreed that administrative blocks are adequate for different departmental offices Mean 3.22 and 3.03 shows that the respondents agreed that the school possess all the requisite gadgets needed to make learning enjoyable. Mean 3.31 and 3.06 shows that the respondents agreed that recreational facilities of the school affords students opportunity to be vast in sports. Mean 3.40 and 3.28 shows that respondents agreed that office equipment for administrative functions are adequate. Mean 3.10 and 3.13 shows that respondents agreed that classroom are sufficient for students to be split into smaller units for effective teaching and learning. This indicated that there is adequacy of school plant on Principals management practices in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question 2

To what extent do principals perceive the availability of school plants management practices in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 2: shows the response of the respondents to research questionnaire item 6-10. Summary of descriptive statistics for principals’ perception on the availability of school plant management practices

	STATEMENTS	MALE PRINCIPALS		FEMALE PRINCIPALS		TOTAL/MEAN		
		M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	RMK
6	The available staff room block is conducive for staff productivity.	3.48	0.87	3.08	0.77	3.28	0.82	A
	Security gadgets are adequately provided by school authority on existing infrastructure.	3.22	0.81	3.28	0.82	3.25	0.81	A
8	Regular supervision of equipment are done by the principal	3.00	0.75	3.03	0.76	3.02	0.76	A
9	The school libraries are often converted into offices as staff rooms.	3.21	0.80	3.36	0.84	3.29	0.83	A
10	Replacement of obsolete materials are easily handled by the state schools board	3.10	0.73	3.13	0.78	3.02	0.76	A
	Grand Mean/SD	16.01	3.96	15.88	3.97	15.86	3.98	

Mean 3.48 and 3.08 shows that the respondents agreed that the available staff room block is conducive for staff productivity. Mean 3.22 and 3.28 shows that the respondents agreed that security gadgets are adequately provided by school authority on existing infrastructure. Mean 3.00 and 3.03 shows that the respondents agreed that regular supervision of equipment are done by the principal. Mean 3.21 and 3.36 shows that the respondents agreed that the school libraries are often converted into offices as staff rooms. Mean 3.26 and 3.08 shows that the respondents agreed that the replacement of obsolete materials are easily handled by the state schools board. Therefore, there is availability of school plant for the effective management practices in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the perception of male and female principals’ on the adequacy of school plant management practices of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 3: shows the analysis of hypothesis 1 and summary of t-test statistics for principals’ perception on the adequacy of school plant management practices

	N	Mean	SD	T-calculation Value	DF	T-Table value	&	Result
Male Principals	100	16.38	247.32	0.4680	398	1.96	0.05	Significant
Female Principals	300	15.53						

The result of the analyzed data in table 3 above shows that the t-calculated value is 0.4680 while the t-table value is 1.96 at 0.5 level of significant. Since the t-calculated value is less than the t-table value the null hypothesis is accepted which shows that there is no significant difference between male and female principals on the adequacy of school plant in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the perception of male and female principals’ on the availability of school plant management practices of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: shows the analysis of hypothesis 2 and summary of t-test statistics for principals’ perception on the availability of school plant management practices

	N	Mean	SD	T-calculation Value	DF	T-Table value	&	Result
Male Principals	100	16.17	251.244	0.1857	398	1.96	0.05	Significant
Female Principals	300	15.83						

The result of the analyzed data in table 4 above showed that t-calculated value is 0.1857 while the t-tables value is 1.96 at 0.5 level of significance. Since the t-calculated value is less than t-table value the null hypothesis is accepted which shows that there is no significant difference between male and female principals on the availability of school plant in public senior secondary school in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

Analysis of data in research question one revealed that male and female principals have perception of the adequacy of school plants in the management practices of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study indicated the adequacy of administrative blocks, such as the staffroom, requisites gadgets for teaching and learning process and apparatus for practical. Supporting the findings, Ikegwuru (2016) citing Ocho noted that quality education is determined by the number of factors in the physical plant including furniture, equipment, and the existence of learning aids like libraries. The findings further revealed that the over-crowded students in a classroom was attributed to inadequate learning space. This is true as the study indicated that the classroom were not sufficient, thereby supporting Enaowho and Eferekeya (2014) who disclosed that provision of facilities such as classroom, Laboratories and workshops are all of immense importance to teaching and learning effectively, and the implementation of educational policy.

The analysis of data further revealed the acceptance of all the null hypothesis with the t-calculated less than the t-table value at 0.05 of significance, thereby showing that there were no significant difference found in the mean perception of male and female principals on the adequacy of school plants, utilization of school plants and availability of school plants in the management practices in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Conclusion

From the findings of this study the following conclusions were drawn that Principals perceive the adequacy of school plants in their management practices. Principals also agreed on the availability of school plants which will mostly yield high performance of students thereby resulting to effective administration and increase in staff productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Recommendation

In the light of the above, the following recommendations were articulated by the researchers

1. The construction of more administrative blocks to accommodate the different staff offices should be built and regular supervision of school plant should be intensified by the state government.
2. The provision of school plants that would enhance teaching and learning processes should be encouraged by the state ministry of education and the government.

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